

Optimizing Use of Multigroup Libraries in SCALE MSR Depletion Analysis

Mohamed Nasser¹, Bojan Petrovic^{1,*}

¹ Georgia Institute of Technology, Nuclear and Radiological Engineering, Atlanta, GA 30332-0745

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803414

ABSTRACT

Molten Salt Reactors (MSRs) are emerging as one of the most promising Generation IV reactor concepts due to their inherent safety, high thermal efficiency, and flexible fuel cycle options. As several U.S. designs advance toward commercialization, both high-fidelity and computationally efficient simulations are required to support licensing and safety analyses. The SCALE code suite provides Monte Carlo continuous energy (CE) and multigroup (MG) transport and depletion capabilities that are widely used for MSR modeling. However, CE depletion calculations are computationally expensive, motivating the evaluation of MG with self-shielding treatments as faster alternatives, potentially without significant accuracy loss. This work investigates the impact of SCALE's MG self-shielding methods, BONAMI and CENTRM with CELLDATA together with Dancoff factor correction on depletion modeling accuracy and computational performance for a graphite-moderated, fluoride salt-cooled MSR unit cell. Results show that the 252-group library provides significantly improved accuracy relative to the 56-group case, maintaining deviations in k_{inf} within ~ 100 pcm of the CE reference throughout depletion. Application of the Dancoff factor correction in CENTRM notably reduced deviation growth over burnup, improving the Δk range from $[-356.1 \text{ pcm}; -152.2 \text{ pcm}]$ down to $[-11.4 \text{ pcm}; 83.2 \text{ pcm}]$ for the 252-group case. In terms of performance, MG depletion reduced total runtime from ~ 98 hours (CE) to ~ 6 hours, representing over a $16\times$ speedup.

Keywords: Monte Carlo multigroup depletion, SCALE, self-shielding, Dancoff factor

1. INTRODUCTION

Molten Salt Reactors (MSRs) are garnering a lot of industry interest due to their fuel cycle, neutron spectra flexibility and potential for enhanced safety. MSRs distinguish themselves from other advanced reactor concepts by dissolving fissile and fertile materials directly into a circulating molten fluoride or chloride salt which also acts as the coolant. This approach enables unique features such as online refueling, actinide management, and improved thermal efficiency. The salts as a coolant provide favorable thermo-physical properties, including high boiling points, low vapor pressures, and excellent heat transfer capabilities, enabling MSRs to operate at higher temperature and lower (ambient) pressures compared to water-cooled reactors giving them larger safety margins [1]. For these reasons, several designs under active development in the United States, ranging from thermal-spectrum concepts such as the Molten Salt Research Reactor (MSRR) [2] pursued by Natura Resources LLC and the Nuclear Energy eXperimental Testing Research Alliance (NEXTRA), to fast-spectrum variants like the Molten Chloride Fast Reactor (MCFR)[3] being pursued by TerraPower.

With these new developments there is growing demand for the modeling of MSRs and consequentially the licensing of MSR design through the U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission (NRC). The SCALE [4] reactor modeling software suite, developed and maintained by Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL), is a commonly utilized tool, by industry and academia, to verify MSR modeling capabilities due to its development and validation under contract with the NRC. Fuel depletion is a significant functional need in the licensing process; both high-fidelity and computationally efficient simulations are required. However, SCALE continuous-energy (CE)

*¹ bojan.petrovic@gatech.edu

depletion takes a long time, for instance, a 2022 paper by Petrovic et al [5] demonstrated that CE depletion was approximately 13.7 times slower than the 252-group and 18.6 times slower than the 56-group simulations for a representative MSRR core model. Similar trends have been observed in [6]. In contrast to CE methods, MG neutron transport utilizes cross sections that are averaged over discrete energy groups that are weighted by the local neutron spectrum, making them sensitive to the material environment. If MG cross sections are generated assuming an infinite-dilution spectrum, they will overestimate resonance absorption in real systems making problem-dependent self-shielding essential to accurately represent resonance absorption effects. This study assesses whether SCALE's MG self-shielding methods can provide accuracy approaching that of CE calculations while significantly reducing computational run time within the scope of graphite-moderated, fluoride salt-cooled MSRs. By using the TRITON (T6-DEPL) sequence, we compare CE and MG transport results employing self-shielding treatments. We examine their effect on reactivity evolution over depletion as well as assess the computational trade-offs for practical use.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Model

This study models a thermal/epithermal graphite-moderated MSR unit cell inspired by the historically significant and successful Molten Salt Reactor Experiment (MSRE) [7] graphite block geometry. This study simplified the unit cell geometry while preserving the graphite and salt volume ratios (as seen in Fig. 1).

Figure 1. MSRE graphite stringer unit cell. (left) and the simplified model used in this study (right)

The fuel element is modeled in an infinite lattice using axial and radial reflection. The fuel salt composition is adjusted to represent a typical modern MSR utilizing HALEU rather than HEU. It is a mixture of LiF–BeF₂–UF₄ consisting of 67.2 mol% LiF, 27.8 mol% BeF₂, and 5.0 mol% UF₄, with lithium enriched to 99.991 wt% ⁷Li. Uranium in UF₄ is enriched to 19.75 wt% ²³⁵U with the balance of 80.25 wt% assumed to be ²³⁸U. The salt density is assumed to be 2.645 g/cm³ at an operating temperature of 900 K. The fuel is depleted to burnup of 100 GWd/tHM over seven years of full-power operation. Constant power irradiation is simulated using fine initial time steps (1–30 days), followed by 24 steps of 60 days each, and lastly 10 steps of 103 days to reach the target burnup.

2.2. SCALE Options and Parameters

All simulations were performed with the TRITON sequence in SCALE 6.3.2, which couples 3D Monte Carlo transport (KENO-VI) with isotopic depletion (ORIGEN). Both ENDF/B-VIII.0 and ENDF/B-VII.1 libraries were employed in CE and MG modes; however, the primary analysis of MG self-shielding treatment employs ENDF/B-VII.1 CE and SCALE's 252-group & 56-group structure. This choice reflects the broader acceptance of ENDF/B-VII.1 as the more reliable library and its longer validation history. A 2022 study by Bostelmann et al. [8] demonstrated that in SCALE 6.2.4, CE calculations of the MSRE benchmark showed that ENDF/B-VIII.0 produced higher ^{235}U neutron multiplicity and capture cross sections, yielding an increase of approximately 265 pcm in keff relative to ENDF/B-VII.1. The depletion parameter ADDNUX, which controls the number of nuclides tracked in self-shielding calculations, was set to ADDNUX = 3 (231 nuclides). The ENDF/B-VII.1 CE case is used as the reference throughout this study.

2.3. MG Self-shielding Treatment and Employing Dancoff Factor in CENTRM

MG self-shielding was treated using either BONAMI, which implements Bondarenko method, or the SCALE CENTRM approach, which computes problem-specific fluxes on a fine energy mesh (10,000-70,000 points) to generate self-shielded multigroup cross sections. A detailed description can be found in the SCALE manual [4]. To improve accuracy, we employed CELLDATA option with both methods. CELLDATA defines unit cell calculations, in an infinite lattice, for generating problem-dependent multigroup cross sections. Furthermore, in this block SCALE incorporating the Dancoff factor (DF) to account for spatial self-shielding between neighboring fuel elements by removing neutrons absorbed in one element from the flux seen by others. Although the XSProc module nominally computes DF from the CELLDATA input using MCDancoff, known issues in the MCDancoff module prevent a DF from being automatically computed. However, the user can specify the DF by using the DAN2PITCH option in the CELLDATA block. Specifically, DAN2PITCH values were varied between 0 and 1.0 in CENTRM, and the resulting initial k_{inf} values were plotted. Then, the DF value was selected for which the multigroup beginning-of-cycle (BOC) transport calculation aligned with the CE BOC calculation, as shown in Figure 2. Specifically, linear and quadratic fits were applied to both the 56g and 252g cases. The positive root of the quadratic fit yielded DF of approximately 0.290 for the 56g run and 0.287 for the 252g run which was subsequently used for the depletion calculation. These DFs were then applied via the DAN2PITCH option in the corresponding MG depletion runs, resulting in initial transport calculations within 3–4 pcm of the CE solution. This work aims to assess whether the initial DF correction remains valid throughout the depletion interval.

Figure 2. k_{inf} vs Dancoff Factor for determining DAN2Pitch value.

2.4. Monte Carlo Parameters & Performance Evaluation Criteria

All simulations used the same number of total histories 10^8 with simulations ranging from 100,000 to 150,000 histories per generation, 10 to 25 inactive generations for source convergence, and 500 to 1000 active generations. Table I summarizes the simulation cases.

Table I. Simulation Matrix

Case ID	XS Library	Self-Shielding Processing	Total Particle histories
CE_8	CE- ENDF8.0	inherent	10^8
CE_7.1	CE -ENDF7.1	inherent	10^8
MG252_CENTRM_8	MG-252g with ENDF8.0	CENTRM	10^8
MG252_CENTRM_7.1	MG-252g with ENDF7.1	CENTRM	10^8
MG252_CENTRM_Lattice	MG-252g with ENDF7.1	CENTRM with lattice-cell resonance self-shielding	10^8
MG252_CENTRM_Lattice_DF	MG-252g with ENDF7.1	CENTRM with lattice-cell resonance self-shielding with Dancoff factor	10^8
MG252_BONAMI	MG-252g with ENDF7.1	BONAMI	10^8
MG252_BONAMI_Lattice	MG-252g with ENDF7.1	BONAMI with lattice-cell resonance self-shielding	10^8
MG252_CENRM_7.1	MG-56g	CENTRM	10^8
MG56_CENTRM_Lattice	MG-56g	CENTRM with lattice-cell resonance self-shielding	10^8
MG56_CENTRM_Lattice_DF	MG-56g	CENTRM with lattice-cell resonance self-shielding with Dancoff factor	10^8
MG56_BONAMI	MG-56g	BONAMI	10^8
MG56_BONAMI_Lattice	MG-56g	BONAMI with lattice-cell resonance self-shielding	10^8

Each simulation produced time-dependent values of infinite multiplication factor (k or k_{inf}). We compared these outputs across cases to assess deviations from the CE reference results. Accuracy was determined by Δk (pcm) range throughout the depletion cycle (as compared to the reference case). Performance was evaluated by total runtime (hours) under identical computational resources. Table II summarizes these results, including transport simulation time ranges throughout depletion (KENO time range) which is the bulk of the total computational time, and total wall runtimes (minutes). Although the simulations were performed on simplified pin cell models, a large number of histories was intentionally used to reduce statistical uncertainties to under 10 pcm for 1σ .

3. RESULTS

3.1. Differences in ENDF Libraries

To compare results of different runs, the Δk relative to the reference case (CE, ENDF/B-VII.1) was plotted at each depletion interval across the burnup. This allows for a direct assessment of the accuracy loss when employing MG self-shielding methods. Figure 3 highlights the performance of ENDF/B-VIII.0 for both CE and MG cases (252-group with CENTRM and lattice-cell resonance self-shielding). The CE Δk begins at -150 pcm, increases to approximately $+100$ pcm, and ultimately converges toward the End-of-Life (EoL) value of the ENDF/B-VII.1 library. In comparison, the MG ENDF/B-VIII.0 cases follow a similar trend but span a broader range, from -400 pcm to -100 pcm, before settling at an EoL value of 150 pcm.

Fig. 3. Relative difference of k_{inf} of the ENDFVIII.0 library to ENDFVII.1 over all depletion intervals (Error bars are $\pm 1\sigma$ RMS).

3.2. Multigroup Self-shielding Treatment

The analysis of MG self-shielding treatments is presented in Figures 4–7. Figure 4 shows Δk for four cases: 252g CENTRM, 252g BONAMI, 56g CENTRM, and 56g BONAMI, all without lattice-cell resonance self-shielding. As expected, accuracy relative to CE is poor. Among these, 252g CENTRM performs best, yet still yields a large EoL deviation of ~ 2000 pcm in k_{inf} . Figure 5 repeats the comparison with lattice-cell resonance self-shielding included. Notably, 252g BONAMI exhibits the best performance, maintaining a nearly linear and consistent Δk throughout the cycle and remaining within 144 pcm of CE. Interestingly, 56g CENTRM outperforms 252g CENTRM when lattice-cell resonance self-shielding is applied, which is counter to expectations. Figure 6 examines the usage of the Dancoff factor to the 252g and 56g CENTRM runs. The DAN2PITCH values used were derived from Figure 2. With Dancoff applied, both cases exhibit nearly zero Δk at BoL, but deviations grow steadily over burnup. A linear fit (figure 7) reveals that the Dancoff correction reduces the slope of Δk growth: from 1.89 to 0.80 pcm/GWd for 252g and from 3.17 to 2.81 pcm/GWd for 56g. For the 252g case, this reduction suggests a more accurate representation of the physical effects throughout the cycle.

Fig. 4. Relative difference of k_{inf} of the MG Self-treatment modes to the reference case over all depletion intervals (Error bars are $\pm 1\sigma$ RMS).

Fig. 5. Relative difference of k_{inf} of the MG Self-treatment modes with CELLDATA to the reference case over all depletion intervals (Error bars are $\pm 1\sigma$ RMS).

Fig. 6. Relative difference of k_{inf} of the MG Self-treatment modes with Dancoff factor to the reference case over all depletion intervals (Error bars are $\pm 1\sigma$ RMS).

Fig. 7. Relative difference of k_{inf} of the MG Self-treatment modes with Dancoff factor to the reference case over all depletion intervals (Error bars are $\pm 1\sigma$ RMS).

3.3. Performance analysis

Table II provides a performance summary for the ENDF/B-VII.1 CE and MG self-shielded cases. All simulations were executed in parallel using 50 cores, except for the MG252_CENTRM_Lattice_DF case; due to memory constraints, this specific run required a reduced core count. TRITON is known to exhibit a memory leakage bug within SCALE 6.3.2 when running in parallel. All simulations were performed on the Idaho National Laboratory (INL) high-performance computing (HPC) system. The specific compute nodes varied between runs due to memory constraints per node and resource availability on the shared HPC system, which complicates a rigorous comparison of parallel performance metrics. Nevertheless, we can compare the total run time of each simulation with the CE depletion requiring ~ 98 hours, whereas the MG cases finished in only 5–6 hours achieving more than a 16x reduction in runtime.

Table II. Performance Matrix

Case ID	Range of K_{inf}	Range of ΔK (pcm)	Range of standard deviation (pcm)	Number of total cores	KENO time per step (mins)	Total time (hr)
CE_7.1	1.27774 to 0.90118	-	-	50	136.8 to 148.8	97.58
MG252_CENTRM_Lattice	1.27422 to 0.89966	-356 to -152	10 to 12	50	5.63 to 6.81	5.46
MG252_CENTRM_Lattice_DF	1.27773 to 0.90197	-11 to 83	10 to 12	25	7.95 to 8.35	6.82
MG252_BONAMI_Lattice	1.27876 to 0.90225	87 to 144	10 to 12	50	5.71 to 6.90	4.48
MG56_CENTRM_Lattice	1.27526 to 0.90203	-252 to 85	9 to 11	50	5.71 to 5.89	5.00
MG56_CENTRM_Lattice_DF	1.27770 to 0.90379	-31 to 262	10 to 12	50	6.19 to 6.49	5.46

The results suggest significant computational advantages of SCALE’s 252-group & 56-group library relative to the CE for MSR. On average, the 252-group library exhibited smaller k_{inf} deviation from the reference solution across burnup, indicating superior accuracy in predicting k_{eff} relative to the 56-group library for the various self-shielding treatments. This outcome is expected, as a finer multigroup structure more accurately captures the local energy-dependent behavior of cross sections. Furthermore, the Dancoff factor correction in SCALE proved highly effective in mitigating the deviation growth over burnup observed in the CELLDATA run—reducing the deviation range from -356.10 to -152.20 down to -11.40 to 83.20 for the 252-group case, and from -252.50 to 85.10 down to -30.80 to 262.10 for the 56-group case.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Results show that the 252-group library with CENTRM and Dancoff correction may offer attractive balance between fidelity and performance, maintaining k_{inf} deviations within ~ 100 pcm of the continuous-energy reference while reducing computational time by more than sixteen-fold. Although the discrepancy in accuracy for the multigroup self-shielded is not negligible, the results show that properly treated MG cross sections can reliably reproduce CE depletion trends which can be used for design and parametric studies in the licensing process. Future work will extend this methodology to more complex geometries and full-core MSR models and assess performance under varying spectral and temperature conditions.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This material is based upon work supported by the National Science Foundation under Grant Number 2306085, titled Georgia Institute of Technology Bridge to the Doctorate Program. This research made use of the resources of the High-Performance Computing Center at Idaho National Laboratory, which is supported by the Office of Nuclear Energy of the U.S. Department of Energy and the Nuclear Science User Facilities under Contract No. DE-AC07-05ID14517 [<https://inl.gov/hpc/>].

REFERENCES

- [1] Generation IV International Forum, “Molten Salt Reactors (MSR),” GIF Portal, accessed Oct. 18, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.gen-4.org/generation-iv-criteria-and-technologies/molten-salt-reactors-msr>
- [2] Abilene Christian University (ACU), “Submittal of the NEXT Lab Molten Salt Research Reactor Licensing Regulatory Engagement Plan,” Document ML20241A071, ACU, (2020).
- [3] K. Kramer et al., “TerraPower’s Molten Chloride Fast Reactor Technology,” 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18467.09768>
- [4] W. A. WIESELQUIST, R. A. LEFEBVRE, EDS., SCALE 6.3.2 User Manual, ORNL/TM-2024/3386, UT-Battelle, Oak Ridge National Laboratory (February 2024).
- [5] B. Petrovic, K. Carberry, J. Faulkner, C. Bayne, and R. Rahaman, “Preliminary Assessment of Parallel Efficiency of SCALE CSAS6 and T6-DEPL Sequences,” in Proceedings of the 13th International Conference of the Croatian Nuclear Society, Zadar, Croatia, Jun. 5–8, 2022, Paper No. 159.
- [6] C. E. Bayne and B. Petrovic, "Molten Salt Reactor Modeling in SCALE: Effects of Multigroup Libraries on Depletion Analysis," in ANS Winter Meeting 2022, Phoenix, AZ, November 13-17, 2022.
- [7] R. C. Robertson, "MSRE Design & Operations Report Part 1: Description of Reactor Design," Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL), Oak Ridge, TN, ORNL-TM-728, Jan. 1965. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.2172/4654707>.
- [8] F. Bostelmann, S. Skutnik, E. Walker, G. Procop, W. Wieselquist, (2021). Modeling of the Molten Salt Reactor Experiment with SCALE. Nuclear Technology. 208. 10.1080/00295450.2021.1943122.